

When Preeclampsia Blinds: Bilateral Retinal Detachment in Hypertensive Pregnancies

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Preeclampsia is a multisystemic hypertensive disorder of pregnancy affecting 5–8% of gestations worldwide and remains a major cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality [1–3]. Visual symptoms occur in up to 25% of patients and are usually transient; however, serous retinal detachment is a rare but vision-threatening complication, occurring in approximately 1–2% of severe cases and up to 10% in eclampsia [4,5]. This condition results from choroidal ischemia and dysfunction of the retinal pigment epithelium secondary to intense arteriolar vasospasm and endothelial damage [6–8].

Case Series: We report three cases of adolescent pregnant patients diagnosed with severe preeclampsia who developed bilateral serous retinal detachment. The mean age was 17 years. All patients presented with headache and acute bilateral visual loss. Retinal detachment was confirmed by fundoscopy and optical coherence tomography (OCT). Management included cesarean section, systemic antihypertensive therapy, and corticosteroid treatment. Intensive care support was required in all cases. Progressive improvement of visual function was documented in each case, with full recovery over 5 to 6 weeks.

Discussion: Although rare, bilateral retinal detachment should be considered in pregnant women presenting with acute visual disturbances in the setting of hypertensive disorders. Prompt diagnosis and timely multidisciplinary management—particularly involving obstetrics, ophthalmology, and intensive care—are key to preventing permanent visual sequelae and ensuring maternal-fetal safety.

Conclusion: Serous bilateral retinal detachment represents a rare but reversible ophthalmic complication of severe preeclampsia. Early recognition and multidisciplinary intervention can lead to complete visual recovery. Obstetricians should maintain a high index of suspicion when managing hypertensive pregnant patients with visual symptoms.

KEYWORDS: Preeclampsia, retinal detachment, pregnancy, visual loss, hypertensive disorders.

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INTRODUCTION

Preeclampsia is a multisystem hypertensive disorder that complicates approximately 5–8% of pregnancies worldwide and remains a leading cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality [1,2]. The pathophysiology involves abnormal trophoblastic invasion of the maternal spiral

arteries, resulting in impaired uteroplacental perfusion and systemic endothelial dysfunction [3–5]. This condition often manifests after 20 weeks of gestation and may progress rapidly to severe disease with multiorgan involvement.

In Mexico, preeclampsia incidence reaches up to 47.3 per 1,000 births and constitutes the primary cause of admission

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to intensive care units for pregnant women [6,7]. According to the World Health Organization, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, including preeclampsia and eclampsia, account for approximately 14% of maternal deaths globally, with significant burden concentrated in Latin America and the Caribbean [8,9]

Ocular involvement occurs in up to 25% of patients with preeclampsia and may include hypertensive retinopathy, serous retinal detachment, papilledema, and vascular occlusions [10–12]. Serous retinal detachment, a rare complication (occurring in 1–2% of severe preeclampsia cases), results from choroidal ischemia secondary to intense arteriolar vasospasm and disruption of the outer blood-retinal barrier [13–15]. This leads to accumulation of subretinal fluid and retinal elevation, threatening visual function.

Clinical symptoms vary from mild blurred vision to acute vision loss, often accompanied by headache and other neurological signs [16]. Timely recognition and multidisciplinary management involving obstetrics, ophthalmology, and critical care are essential to optimize maternal and fetal outcomes, as well as to preserve vision.

This case series describes three adolescent patients with severe preeclampsia complicated by bilateral serous retinal detachment, highlighting the importance of early diagnosis and integrated care in this vulnerable population.

CASE REPORTS

Between March 2021 and March 2024, a total of 2554 pregnant patients with hypertensive disorders were attended

at the Gynecology and Obstetrics Department of Hospital General Doctor Agustín O’Horán, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico. Among these, 956 patients were diagnosed with severe preeclampsia and 32 with HELLP syndrome. Within this cohort, three adolescent patients developed bilateral serous retinal detachment associated with severe preeclampsia.

Case 1:

A 17-year-old primigravida without prenatal care presented at 36.1 weeks of gestation with sudden-onset headache and visual disturbances. Blood pressure measured 170/110 mmHg. Severe preeclampsia was diagnosed with a focal neurological deficit affecting visual fields. Cesarean delivery was performed under general anesthesia without intraoperative complications; estimated blood loss was 300 mL. Postpartum, the patient exhibited persistent bilateral visual loss. Admission to the intensive care unit showed stable neurological status (FOUR score 18). Laboratory findings revealed thrombocytopenia (platelets 69,000/ μ L) and elevated liver enzymes.

Ophthalmologic evaluation revealed bilateral serous retinal detachment confirmed by fundoscopy (*Figure 1*). Retinal assessment showed bullous detachment with macular involvement in both eyes (*Figures 2 and 3*). Spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (OCT) demonstrated increased macular thickness and hyporeflexive subretinal fluid consistent with serous retinal detachment (*Figure 4*).

Figure 1. Fundoscopy of the right eye showing funnel-shaped retinal detachment.

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Figures 2 and 3. Retinology evaluation showing bullous retinal detachment involving the macula.

Figure 4. Spectral-domain optical coherence tomography showing increased macular thickness and subretinal fluid.

Treatment included oral and periorbital corticosteroids (prednisone and dexamethasone) along with antihypertensive

therapy. After 4 days in the ICU, she was transferred to the obstetrics ward. At follow-up, fundus examination revealed

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no optic disc edema, and hyperpigmented areas were observed at the sites of previous detachment (Elsching spots)

(Figure 5). Complete visual recovery was confirmed by week six, and the patient was discharged from both services.

Figure 5. Fundoscopy showing regular optic disc and pigmented lesions (Elsching spots) at previous detachment sites.

Case 2:

An 18-year-old G2P1 without prenatal care presented at 37.4 weeks gestation with a 4-hour history of blurred vision, headache, and vomiting. Blood pressure was 160/110 mmHg. Diagnosis of severe preeclampsia with visual field deficits was made. Cesarean section under regional anesthesia was performed; blood loss was 350 mL.

Ophthalmologic assessment showed bilateral funnel-shaped serous retinal detachment. Visual acuity was limited to counting fingers at 50 cm. Retinal evaluation confirmed macular involvement. Treatment included antihypertensives and periorbital dexamethasone. After 5 days in the ICU, she was discharged to the ward. Follow-up fundoscopy showed resolution of the detachment with residual hyperpigmentation and preserved macular anatomy. Full visual recovery occurred by week five.

Case 3:

A 16-year-old primigravida without prenatal care presented at 36.5 weeks gestation with frontal headache and acute visual

loss. Blood pressure was 150/90 mmHg. She underwent cesarean delivery under regional anesthesia for severe preeclampsia with neurological involvement. Blood loss was 450 mL.

Laboratory analysis showed thrombocytopenia (platelets 47,000/ μ L) and elevated liver enzymes. Fundoscopy revealed bullous and funnel-shaped bilateral serous retinal detachment with macular involvement. OCT confirmed subretinal fluid accumulation. The patient received oral and periorbital corticosteroids in addition to blood pressure control.

After 4 days in the ICU, she was transferred to the obstetrics floor. At follow-up, retinal reattachment and normal fundus were documented. Corticosteroids were discontinued by week six with complete visual recovery.

All patients received discharge instructions with scheduled follow-up in obstetrics and ophthalmology clinics. No persistent visual deficits or retinal anomalies were reported at final evaluation.

A summary of the clinical, biochemical, and ophthalmologic characteristics of the three patients is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Clinical Characteristics of Patients With Severe Preeclampsia and Bilateral Retinal Detachment

Variable	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Age (years)	17	18	16
Gravidity/Parity	G1P0	G2P1	G1P0

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Variable	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Prenatal care	No	No	No
Gestational age (weeks)	36.1	37.4	36.5
Blood pressure (mmHg)	170/110	160/110	150/90
Chief complaint	Headache, visual loss	Visual loss, headache, vomiting	Headache, visual loss
Platelet count ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	69	92	47
Liver enzymes (AST/ALT) (U/L)	54 / 21	43 / 18	48 / 56
Mode of delivery	Cesarean section	Cesarean section	Cesarean section
Anesthesia type	General	Regional	Regional
Blood loss during delivery (mL)	300	350	450
ICU stay (days)	4	5	4
Visual acuity (initial)	Counting fingers at 50 cm	Counting fingers at 50 cm	Counting fingers at 50 cm
Ophthalmologic findings	Funnel & bullous detachment	Funnel detachment	Bullous detachment
OCT findings	Macular edema, subretinal fluid	Not specified	Macular edema, subretinal fluid
Steroid treatment	Oral & periorbital	Periorbital	Oral & periorbital
Outcome	Full visual recovery at 6 weeks	Full visual recovery at 5 weeks	Full visual recovery at 6 weeks

Table 1

This table summarizes demographic, clinical, and laboratory data, delivery characteristics, retinal findings, and treatment outcomes in three adolescent patients with severe preeclampsia complicated by bilateral serous retinal detachment.

DISCUSSION

Preeclampsia is a complex multisystem disorder characterized by hypertension and end-organ dysfunction after 20 weeks of gestation. Its incidence remains high in developing regions, including Mexico, where it constitutes a leading cause of maternal ICU admissions and mortality [1,6,9]. Ocular manifestations, while often mild and transient, can occasionally progress to serious complications such as serous retinal detachment, threatening permanent vision loss [4,10,13].

Serous retinal detachment in preeclampsia is attributed to choroidal ischemia caused by intense arteriolar vasospasm and subsequent breakdown of the outer blood-retinal barrier, leading to subretinal fluid accumulation [7,11,14]. This pathophysiology aligns with our cases, where all patients presented with bilateral detachment and associated visual symptoms. The adolescent age group may represent a vulnerable population due to delayed prenatal care and more severe disease presentation, as observed in our series.

Early detection of visual disturbances and prompt ophthalmological assessment are critical. Fundoscopy and optical coherence tomography (OCT) remain the diagnostic standards, allowing confirmation and monitoring of retinal status [5,12]. Treatment is primarily supportive, focusing on blood pressure control and delivery of the fetus to resolve the underlying disease process. Adjunct corticosteroid therapy,

as applied in our cases, may aid in reducing retinal inflammation and edema, although evidence remains limited [4,15].

Our findings corroborate previous reports emphasizing the reversible nature of retinal detachment with timely intervention, highlighting the importance of a multidisciplinary approach involving obstetricians, ophthalmologists, and intensivists to optimize both maternal and fetal outcomes [2,4,10]. Raising awareness of this rare but serious complication is crucial, especially in regions with high preeclampsia prevalence and limited prenatal care access.

Further studies are warranted to clarify the role of corticosteroids and refine management protocols to prevent long-term visual sequelae in this patient population.

CONCLUSION

Bilateral serous retinal detachment is a rare but serious ocular complication of severe preeclampsia, predominantly affecting young pregnant women with hypertensive crises. Early recognition of visual symptoms and timely multidisciplinary management, including prompt delivery and appropriate ophthalmologic care, are essential to prevent permanent vision loss. Our case series demonstrates that with comprehensive supportive treatment, including blood pressure control and corticosteroid therapy, complete visual recovery is achievable. Increased awareness and vigilance are crucial for improving maternal and fetal outcomes in regions with high preeclampsia incidence.

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